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**Mechanical Engineering: An International
Journal (MEIJ)**

ISSN: 2349 - 2651

<http://airccse.com/meij/index.html>

INVESTIGATION OF SPRING BACK BEHAVIOR OF SS-304 STEEL AND ITS BI-LAYER MATERIAL IN V BENDING

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ABSTRACT

Components press formed from layered or laminated metallic materials have wide engineering application in aerospace, automobile, electrical, electronic and process industries. High strength ferrous metals are widely used in automobile industries for utilization of its high strength to weight ratio. Such high strength metals offer poor formability. Formability of such metals can be improved by applying a layer of metal having higher formability. This paper deals with springback behavior of a laminated stainless steel and aluminum in V bending. Investigation of bending characteristics like thickness ratio and bending angles of sheet before/after springback is carried out in this paper. First part of this paper is on numerical analysis for springback prediction of laminated sheet. In second part, experiments are performed for different cases on V bending machine. The experimental results show that springback of sheet metal laminate is greatly affected by relative position of strong/weak layers and thickness ratio of each layer.

KEYWORDS

Springback; High strength steel; Layered material; V bending.

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